

RESEARCH REPORT

October, 2024

TREPA Series 28-2024

**STUDY GUIDE: Disease Awareness at
Livestock/ Wildlife Interface**

PREPARED BY:

Richard Burroughs, Pieter Tomas Nel, and Peter Menze

Hamming

TREPA

**Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals**

TREPA PUBLICATION SERIES

This publication is one of a series of scholarly products resulting from investigations of human dimensions of global environmental change. The Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals studies risk at the intersection of human-wildlife conflicts and diseases of animals using a team science approach.

A LIST OF TREPA PUBLICATIONS MAY BE OBTAINED BY ACCESSING OUR WEBSITE AT:

www.conservationcriminology.com/trepa/

CITE THIS DOCUMENT:

R.E.J Burroughs, P.T. Nel, and P.M. Hamming
*Study Guide: Disease Awareness t Livestock/
Wildlife Interface*. Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People and Animals. Department
of Geographical Sciences, College of Behavioral
and Social Sciences, University of Maryland,
College Park. College Park, MD. 96 pp.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The development of the course was made possible through the collaboration of various people. We would like to acknowledge Dr. Meredith L. Gore, Ms. Natalia Munoz Cassolis, Dr. Henriette van Heerden, Dr. Annette Hübschle, Dr. Juan Martin Dabezies, Dr. Kevin Curtin, and Dr. Barb Wolfe for their contributions towards making this study guide a success.

This course was developed on the foundation of an existing course presented as part of the Southern African Wildlife College (SAWC) Hearing for Health Course. Pieter Nel is the lead on the Hearing for Health Course and was very generous to share the course materials with us and support the course design.

The research, methods, and analysis detailed in this document were reviewed and granted approval by the (i) the Institutional Review Boards of the University of Maryland, College Park, University of Texas Austin, University of Alabama, and Colorado State University, (ii) Witwatersrand University's Human Research Ethics Committee (non-medical) H24/03/10, and (iv) the Office of Human Research Oversight OHRO Log Number E05089. The project or effort depicted was or is sponsored by the Department of Defense, Defense Threat Reduction Agency. The content of the information does not necessarily reflect the position or the policy of the federal government, and no official endorsement should be inferred.

INTRODUCTION

The TREPA (Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals) research project aims to fill knowledge gaps regarding the intersectionality of risks for zoonotic diseases of pandemic potential and the wildlife use and trade with a One Health approach. TREPA is a 5-year project that started in September 2022.

This document contains the materials designed as part of the TREPA project. It is intended to be a study guide to present the disease course called “Disease Awareness at Livestock/Wildlife Interface”. The development of the course was led by the Southern African Wildlife College using their knowledge and network as an adult education institute. The purpose of the institute is to equip people with the necessary knowledge and applied skills to conserve and protect Africa’s natural resources and its biodiversity. The focus of the developed course is to create awareness of zoonotic disease. The course makes participants aware of major diseases in the region and their impact on wildlife, livestock, and people. Apart from knowledge about zoonotic diseases, participants learn how to decrease the potential health, social, and economic risk that these diseases may have.

CONTENTS

CONTENTS.....	5
1. COURSE OUTLINE	7
2. ONE HEALTH.....	10
3. FUNCTIONAL ANATOMY	12
4. BASIC EPIDEMIOLOGY	18
5. INTRODUCTION TO UNDERSTANDING DISEASE.	23
6. POSTMORTEM EXAMINATION	26
7. DISEASE CONTROL REGULATIONS	29
8. DISEASE CAUSING ORGANISMS	31
8.1 Bacteria	31
8.2 Viruses.....	32
8.3 Protozoa	33
8.4 Fungi.....	35
8.5 Algae.....	37
9. VIRAL DISEASES	39
9.1 Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)	39
9.2 Rift Valley Fever	42
9.3. Malignant Catarrhal Fever	43
9.5 Rabies.....	48
9.7 Avian influenza.....	54
9.8 Mpox Disease.....	56
10. BACTERIAL DISEASES.....	57
10.1 Anthrax.....	57
10.2 Tuberculosis	64
10.3 Brucellosis (Contagious abortion).....	68
11. PROTOZOAL DISEASE	71
11.1 Trypanosomiasis /Trypanosomosis.....	71
11.2 Corridor Disease and East Coast Fever	72
12. NEW DISEASES	75
12.1 Peste des petits ruminants (PPR).....	75
13. EXTERNAL PARASITES.....	77

13.1 Ticks.....	77
13.2 Fleas and lice	81
13.3 Flies	83
13.4 Mosquitoes and midges.....	86
13.5 Mites	87
14. INTERNAL PARASITES OR WORMS.....	89
15. FUNGAL INFECTIONS.....	91
16. NUTRITIONAL CONDITIONS	92
17. POISONINGS.....	93
17.1 Naturally occurring poisons	93
17.2 Plant toxicity	94
FINAL CONSIDERATIONS.....	96

1. COURSE OUTLINE

Day 1

Morning session (4 Hours – with a tea break in between)

Welcome and greet participants

1. Introduction – aims and objectives of the course, course program.
2. One Health principles
3. Basic functional anatomy and physiology
4. Basic epidemiology, immunity and vaccines

Afternoon session (3 Hours)

5. An introduction to understanding disease
 - What is disease or illness?
 - How do we know that an animal is ill?
6. Importance of postmortem examinations.
7. Why do countries have different disease control regulations?
8. Causative agents of disease – bacteria, viruses, protozoa, algae, other

Day 2

Morning session (4 Hours – with a tea break in between)

Quick discussion session - recap of previous day discussions (10 mins)

9. Viral diseases
 - Foot and mouth disease
 - Rift Valley fever
 - Bovine malignant fever (MCF/Snotsiekte)
 - African swine fever
 - Rabies
 - Rabbit hemorrhagic disease
 - Avian influenza
 - Mpox
10. Bacterial diseases
 - Anthrax
 - Tuberculosis
 - Brucellosis

Afternoon Practical session (2 Hours)

Postmortem examination – practical session

- Collection of specimens – ticks, formalin specimens
- Making of blood smears
- Staining of blood smears
- Data collection
- Importance of metadata

Day 3

Morning session (4 Hours – With a tea break in between)

Quick discussion session – recap of previous day discussions (10 mins)

11. Protozoal diseases

- 12.1 Trypanosomosis
- 12.2 Theileria – Corridor disease, East Coast fever

12. New diseases:

- Peste des petits ruminants

Afternoon session (3 Hours)

Divide the class into 3 groups of 5 each, with 5 – 10-minute presentations.

Possible topics:

- a. What are the factors that will contribute to the incidence and diagnosis of rabies in your area, and how would you go about confirming this?
- b. What are the factors that will contribute to the incidence and diagnosis of anthrax in your area, and how would you go about confirming this?
- c. What are the factors that will contribute to the incidence and diagnosis of bovine tuberculosis in your area, and how would you go about confirming this?

Day 4

Morning session (4 Hours – With a tea break in between)

Other diseases or conditions that can influence health.

13. External parasites

- Ticks
- Fleas
- Flies
- Mosquitoes and midges
- Mites / mange

14. Internal parasites

- Roundworms
- Tapeworms and flukes

15. Fungal infections

16. Nutritional / malnutrition / drought and mineral imbalances.

17. Poisonings

- Organic
- Plant toxicity
- Algal blooms

Concluding remarks

- What are you trying to achieve?
- Where are you going to go for help?
- Where are the samples going to go?
- Where is your closest State Vet office or AHT office?
- Who is going to sponsor specialist analysis?

The course ends with an overall feedback session (20 minutes). At all stages, the lectures will be based on promoting a One Health and ecosystem approach.

My notes...

2. ONE HEALTH

Although not new, an approach to understanding disease or disease processes is the concept of One Health. This approach is not always understood or adopted in many countries. This philosophy looks at disease in a comprehensive way that includes animals (wild or domestic), humans, and the environment. Unless there is a unified way of looking at all 3 aspects, there will never be a truly detailed understanding of the disease issues and the steps that must be taken to rectify them.

In Africa and the developing world, this means that investigating disease without understanding people or communities in this approach will not ultimately provide meaningful insights.

Having said that, it is very difficult to unpack and analyze all the components that are required to develop a truly One Health understanding of disease.

The Centre for Disease Control (CDC) defines One Health as:

One Health is a collaborative, multisectoral, and transdisciplinary approach — working at the local, regional, national, and global levels — with the goal of achieving optimal health outcomes, recognizing the interconnection between people, animals, plants, and their shared environment.

Figure 2.1. Diagram of the inter-relationships between wildlife/animal health, human health, and environmental health. <https://doi.org/10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.145172>

Human populations are growing and expanding into new geographic areas. As a result, more people live in close contact with wild and domestic animals, both livestock and pets. Animals play an important role in our lives, whether for food, fiber, livelihoods, travel, sport, education, or companionship. Close contact with animals and their environments provides more opportunities

for diseases to pass between animals and people. Diseases that spread from animals to man are known as zoonoses or zoonotic diseases.

The earth has experienced changes in climate and land use, such as deforestation and intensive farming practices. Disruptions in environmental conditions and habitats can provide new opportunities for diseases to pass to animals.

The movement of people, animals, and animal products has increased from international travel and trade. As a result, diseases can spread quickly across borders and around the globe, causing epidemics of this disease in various countries.

These changes have led to the spread of existing or known (endemic) and new or emerging zoonotic diseases, which are diseases that can spread between animals and people. Every year, millions of people and animals around the world are affected by zoonotic diseases.

3. FUNCTIONAL ANATOMY

In order to understand what causes disease in animals, we first need to know what disease is. Disease (also known as sickness) is any process that interferes with the way the different parts of the body work and look.

The basic unit is the **cell**, consisting of many different types. The types of blood cells, for example, can include those in **Figure 3.1** below:

Figure 3.1. Kinds of red blood cells. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

Various systems of the body:

A. The nervous system

The nervous system controls most aspects of body function either directly through an extensive network of nerves or through the effects of hormones. Nerve impulses cause rapid responses to changing conditions. Specific hormones are secreted into the blood, and there is a delay in response, but their effects can take longer.

The nervous system can be divided into three sections:

1. **The central nervous system (CNS):**

The central nervous system includes the brain and spinal cord.

Figure 3.2. Diagram of the brain. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

2. The **peripheral nervous system**:

Peripheral nerves form a network of fibers throughout the body that communicate with the central nervous system (CNS).

Figure 3.3 Diagram of nerve distribution. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

3. The **autonomic nervous system – voluntary and involuntary**

The basic cell is the neuron, but it functions at synapses (joins between nerve cells) with the aid of neurotransmitters

Reflexes are controlled by different nerve pathways to produce a response. Reflexes is an action to a stimuli taken without thinking about it. For example, if you burn your hand you pull it back very fast without the need to think about it.

Figure 3.4 Diagram of a nerve cell. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

B. The cardiovascular system

This consists of the heart and a circulatory system, which carries the blood throughout the body. The mammalian heart consists of four chambers; two atria and two ventricles. The circulatory system is made up of arteries and veins. It acts like a pump but is subject to electrical activity that connects to the rest of the body.

Figure 3.5 Diagram of the circulatory system. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

Figure 3.6 Diagram of the nervous supply to the heart. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

C. Pulmonary system

The pulmonary system is responsible for respiration and is responsible for gas exchange – absorption of oxygen into the body on inspiration (inhalation) and expulsion of carbon dioxide from the body on expiration (exhalation). The pulmonary system consists of :

- Lungs,
- Alveoli and
- Trachea

Figure 3.7. Diagram of the respiratory system. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

Gas in the lungs typically gives normal lungs a spongy feel. If they do not feel spongy, this indicates damage or disease of some sort. Respiration is regulated by the brain, mostly without our not even being aware of it.

Air is passed through the trachea and bronchi into the final pouches or alveolar sacs where gaseous exchange takes place. (see [Figure 3.8](#))

Figure 39-7

Respiratory unit. (Redrawn from Miller WS: The Lung. Springfield, Ill: Charles C Thomas, 1947.)

Figure 3.8. Diagram of alveolar sacs. (https://www.brainkart.com/article/Diffusion-of-Gases-Through-the-Respiratory-Membrane_19561/)

D. Digestive system and other organs in the abdominal cavity

Digestion is the process whereby food is consumed, digested, and absorbed by the body.

The organs that are involved are the stomach and intestines (also called the gastro-intestinal tract or GIT), liver, and pancreas. The liver is responsible for secreting bile salts to assist with digestion in the intestine and is also responsible for detoxifying by-products of metabolism and some toxic substances. The pancreas is responsible for stabilizing the level of sugar in the body. The function of the kidney is mainly filtration of the blood, and also for excretion of some toxic substances.

The arrangement of the GIT differs substantially between groups of animals.

In carnivores and primates, a simple stomach is responsible for initial digestion with the assistance of hydrochloric acid. This food is then further metabolized and absorbed in the small intestine, and to some extent in the large intestine or colon (see **Figure 3.9**)

A. Gastrointestinal tract of a carnivore or primate

1. Stomach
2. Small intestine
3. Caecum
4. Colon
5. Rectum

Figure 3.9. Diagram of a simple stomach (carnivore, primate). (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs 2012)

Herbivores have the most complex arrangement of gastro-intestinal tract. Two forms exist – the foregut fermenters (which include all cattle, sheep, antelope, giraffe and buffalo) and the hind gut fermenters (which include all horse species, zebra, elephant, rhino and hippo).

In hindgut fermenters, little digestion takes place in the stomach or small intestine. The majority of the digestion takes place in an enlarged caecum and colon (large intestine). Fermentation of food is performed by beneficial bacteria or protozoa in the caecum and then absorbed in the large intestine (See **Figure 3.10**)

B. Gastro-intestinal tract of a hind gut fermenter – rhino, elephant, zebra

1. Stomach
2. Small intestine
3. Caecum
4. Colon
5. Rectum

Figure 3.10. Diagram of the intestines of a hind-gut fermenter. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012)

Ruminants or foregut fermenters have a different arrangement. All food is processed in a 3 or 4 chambered rumen where the food is fermented by beneficial bacteria and protozoa, and then absorbed in the small intestine (see **Figure 3.11**). They also regurgitate some of this rumen content back into their mouths to re-chew the rumen contents and swallow it again. This happens repeatedly and serves to promote digestion.

C. Gastrointestinal tract of a ruminant

1. Stomach
2. Small intestine
3. Caecum
4. Colon
5. Rectum

Figure 3.11. Diagram of the gastro-intestinal tract of a ruminant. (Adapted from Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs, 2012).

Literature quoted: Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs (2012). *The Chemical and Physical restraint of Wild Animals*. 2nd edition. Greyton, South Africa.

4. BASIC EPIDEMIOLOGY

A. Balance between host, disease and environment

Disease causing organisms can be split up into a variety of organism and chemical agents, and all have different ways of existing in the environment and infecting animals.

The most common disease-causing organisms we will be discussing are those caused by bacteria and viruses. Protozoa, fungi and algae can also play a role.

Many of these organisms live in soil or other substrates such as water, decayed leaves, etc. Under certain circumstances their microhabitats are destroyed, and they may be consumed by animals or people where they have may play a role as a disease-causing organism.

In a stable natural system, there is a balance between the environment, parasites, disease causing organisms and their host species. All animals or hosts of an infection usually have a natural immunity to that disease-causing organism. Under certain conditions however that immunity can be compromised so that the disease swamps the hosts immune responses. When these disease outbreaks get out of control and affect a large proportion of the population, we refer to this as an epidemic.

There are three main causes leading to outbreaks of disease:

- Introducing species into an area where they do not naturally occur.
- Introduction of new host species.
- Disturbances or changes to the environment.

A typical stable situation is depicted in [Figure 4.1](#) below.

Figure 4.1. Diagram of the inter-relationship between host, disease/parasite or condition, and the environment. https://cf.son.umaryland.edu/NURS467/pic/epidemiological_triangle.png

Two kinds of diseases are defined:

- Infectious diseases
- Contagious diseases

Many of these diseases are borne from animal to animal by microscopic water droplets, and ingestion or inhalation of these organisms result in rapid infection. These are described as infectious diseases.

Some are spread by direct contact between animals, and are referring to as contagious diseases.

Sometimes diseases are spread by both aerosol transmission and direct contact. Other diseases are transmitted by a vector such as a tick or mosquito – here the parasite undergoes a developmental stage in this vector. If the vector is not present or eliminated, that disease cannot spread.

B. Immunology

An animal's ability to withstand infection is often genetically predetermined, but equally, some animals are genetically predetermined to be susceptible to a disease. Environmental, habitat, and nutritional factors influence this.

The immune system of an animal is complex. The first lines of defense are both white blood cells and antibodies, which can be present on the mucous membranes of the nasal cavity, mouth, and lungs.

Figure 4.2. Kinds of white blood cells. (Adapted from Kock & Burroughs, 2012)

The white blood cells, particularly the neutrophils, have the function of targeting a foreign disease particle, (virus or bacterium), engulfing it, and destroying it (See [Figure 4.3](#)). Other cells such as lymphocytes are memory cells and produce antibodies against that particular organism (see [Figure 4.4](#)).

Phagocytosis

Figure 4.3. A white blood cell (neutrophil) about to engulf a group of bacteria.
[Stock.adobe.com](https://www.adobe.com/stock/230000000/230000000.html) - Tang Yan Song, 2023

Figure 4.4. Figure of antibodies surrounding a virus. (<https://newatlas.com/science/covid-autopsy-study-virus-brain-body/>)

When the disease particles are in massive quantities, they swamp the immune response, and the infected animal develops disease. The animal can either survive or die, depending on the disease organism and the host animal. If the infection recurs, and the animal has survived the first round

of infection, massive amounts of antibodies can be produced very quickly that will control the re-infection, leading to a better chance of survival.

c. Vaccines

Vaccines are derivatives of the disease-causing organism in some way that stimulates the immune system to produce massive amounts of antibodies to withstand an infection. These have been developed over many decades of research, and are subject to strict quality protocols. Some vaccines however have side-effects, and if used incorrectly, can induce clinical disease.

There are a number of ways of doing this.

- a. Killed vaccines. Here a solution of the organism is killed with formalin, amongst others, but it still retains its ability to produce antibodies. This is the safest form of vaccine. Rabies vaccine is an example of this.
- b. Live vaccines. These are weakened or modified in a way that they do not induce disease but stimulates the body to produce antibodies. Foot-and-mouth disease vaccine is an example.
- c. mRNA vaccines. COVID-19 vaccine is an example of a genetically engineered vaccine.

Vaccines are critical in our tools to combat some diseases, but they have limitations in how they have been produced, stored, as well as safety aspects. Some vaccines are available in a liquid form in a bottle or vial, others are available as a freeze-dried pellet that needs to be mixed with a special water or diluent before they can be administered.

Other forms of vaccine are available as well – e.g., intra-nasal spray.

They also must be kept under fridge conditions – the so-called 'cold chain'. If the vaccines are heated above a certain level, usually 2 – 3 degrees C, they lose their effectivity and are useless. This is one of the biggest reasons why outbreaks of disease still occur in populations of animals that have already been vaccinated.

5. INTRODUCTION TO UNDERSTANDING DISEASE.

Diseases can affect many animals of the same species, but they may also affect other species, and of interest to us, wildlife species. Diseases can sometimes spread over into domestic animals, with severe economic complications, and thus have severe restrictions imposed on the wildlife that may be carrying these diseases. Diseases can be transmitted from animals to man, which are called zoonosis, but humans can also transmit diseases to animals, including wildlife.

How do you recognize and start looking for disease?

In domestic animals that one can see and handle on a daily basis, early signs of disease can be readily seen and identified. In wild animals, it is often very difficult. It is not always easy to get close to live animals, and then the following is important:

- Observation of the animal
- Knowledge of normal anatomy
- Knowledge of normal behavior
- How close with they allow you to get?
- The most important feature here is that you need to know what normal looks like, and to understand how the body and its various components work.
- Animals that are hurt – why have they been hurt; do they have an underlying disease issue?
- Animals that look thin, or have an abnormal appearance

The following photos below are for discussion purposes:

- Abnormal condition or swelling

Roy Bengis, 2019. (<https://rr-africa.woah.org/app/uploads/2019/11/bengis2.pdf>)

- Altered skin appearance

Roy Bengis, 2019. (<https://rr-africa.woah.org/app/uploads/2019/11/bengis2.pdf>)

- Abnormal behavior patterns

Roy Bengis, 2019, (<https://rr-africa.woah.org/app/uploads/2019/11/bengis2.pdf>)

In live animals, remember that they are part of a population or herd and that external factors may play a role as well. Never forget that the habitat and ecosystem in which they live can have a major impact on them.

As far as carcasses or dead animals are concerned, the approach to cutting up a carcass is significant. Factors that will play a role here will include:

- Where is the carcass in relation to water or normal habitat
- Where is the carcass in relation to people?
- How old is the carcass, how long has it been there?
- Is it fresh, is it bloated?
- Blood streaming from the nose, anus?
- Position of the neck and head?
- Are there scavengers around – vultures, lions, hyenas?
- How safe is it for me to approach?
- What steps do I need to take for my own disease risk safety (biosecurity – boots, gloves, mask)

- Can I take samples, and what samples?
- Is it safe to open up the carcass?
- Most importantly, what must I do to ensure that I do not spread this disease further if it is an infectious disease?
- How do I protect myself after taking samples or opening up the carcass – washing, disinfection?
- What containers or kits do I have to take samples?
- Where do I take the samples to?
- What information do I need to take with the samples?

Ecosystem processes such as rainfall, soil type, habitat type or change of habitat and thus nutrient balance can play a significant role. What you are looking at today in terms of sick animals may be the result of ecosystem changes that have been many years in the making and trying to understand what makes these differences or changes may be significant.

6. POSTMORTEM EXAMINATION

(Adapted from Mitchell, Foggin and Kock, 2021. Necropsy Techniques. In: Kock, Meltzer & Burroughs (2021) (Eds). The Chemical and Physical Restraint of African Wild Animals. Greyton, South Africa.

Postmortem examination is also called necropsy. In humans, the term autopsy is more commonly used. Although beyond the scope of this course, it is useful to know the function of a postmortem examination, and some of the general rules for performing such a procedure. Necropsy procedures are similar for all mammals, apart from some differences in sampling of the gastrointestinal tract.

A detailed macroscopic or general examination is performed on all organs, and samples are collected for a variety of reasons. Some samples are cut into extremely thin slices, stained, and subject to microscopic examination. Someone who is specifically trained then looks for specific changes in cellular organization and structure.

In addition to this, obtaining a full history is critically important, as is an environmental examination where the necropsy is performed. Samples are then also taken for chemical analysis, and organisms grown to show that they are bacteria, viruses, yeasts, toxins and nutritional analysis.

GENERAL RULES OF NECROPSY

1. Do not touch necropsy specimens with bare hands. Always wear gloves. If you tear or puncture a glove, get a replacement.
2. Photograph all lesions if possible. Remove gloves when taking images.
3. Do not smoke, eat or answer your cell phone during the necropsy examination.
4. There are several acceptable ways of carrying out a necropsy examination. Proceed methodically, conducting a necropsy the same way each time to avoid omissions and to become familiar with the normal appearance of tissues and organs.
5. Do not cut directly across hair, as this dulls the knives. Roll the skin back and cut underneath, using the full sweep of the blade. Do not cut toward yourself or others and keep knives sharp with the sharpening steel.
6. Treat tissues, particularly delicate tissues, including the brain, pancreas, lung and intestine, as gently as you would in surgery. This ensures that handling damage is kept to a minimum so that histological interpretation is maximized.
7. Use water sparingly on tissues as it alters the color. Only wash specimens after representative samples have been taken for microscopic examination as washing causes artifacts.
8. Never stand under a hanging carcass.
9. Wet the carcass and working surfaces before beginning necropsy examinations with a standard disinfectant such as F10 or Virkon, or if these are not available use water. This reduces contamination of the carcass by hair/fur. A disinfectant should be part of your kit, even if in small volumes.

It is important to have a basic knowledge on how to conduct a necropsy, and suitable tools, both in the field or indoors. (Photo credits above, Emily Mitchell)

Figure 6.1 Different methods of conducting a necropsy. Above a large carcass is open with an ax. The images above represent a necropsy of a thinner-skinned animal. (Photo credits above, Michael D. Kock)

Summarized procedure for opening up a carcass:

Follow the guidelines as above, and then:

- Inspect the carcass of any signs of damage or predation.
- Check for bloody discharges from the mouth or anus.
- Cut a piece of the ear and squeeze out some blood onto the cut surface.
- Make a blood smear from the blood spot.
- If there is no indication or knowledge of an anthrax outbreak in the area, the carcass can be opened.
- At all stages, look for unusual or abnormal signs on any organ or group of organs.
- Place the animal on its right-hand side.

- Cut the skin open from throat along the belly to the anus.
- Make incisions along the insides of the legs.
- Separate the subcutaneous layer of the skin from the rest of the body.
- Separate off the front and hind legs.
- Open up the abdomen carefully, making sure that you do not open the stomach or rumen at this stage.
- Expose all the abdominal organs as they lie in the abdomen.
- Penetrate the diaphragm.
- Using cutters, cut through the ribs close to attachment to the spine.
- Turn the opened rib cage up toward the spine so that you can see the heart and lungs.
- Working from under the tongue area, cut out the tongue, trachea and esophagus. Proceed until the heart and lungs can be removed (the so-called pluck).
- With the pluck still attached, remove the rest of the abdominal organs.
- Take these out and examine on a table or flat surface.

You are now able to examine these all these organs individually – tongue, trachea, esophagus, lungs heart, stomach/rumen, the rest of the gastro-intestinal tract, liver, spleen, pancreas, and kidney.

Note the difference or expected difference with regard to the gastrointestinal tract of the various species.

7. DISEASE CONTROL REGULATIONS

Why do countries have different disease control regulations? Each country has the right to determine their own disease regulations and policies. This is largely dependent on trade objectives.

A country's disease status as far as infected or free from a particular disease depends on surveillance. Most countries in the world are signatories to the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH). As part of this process, they have to motivate WOAH or other trading partners that they have done sufficient surveillance to declare themselves free of a disease, or in the case of a new outbreak, infected with the disease.

A good example is Foot-and-Mouth disease (FMD). South Africa has FMD infected and free zones. International trade is only allowed to take place from these free zones, unless the product has been treated in some way to make it non-infective, i.e. tanning a hide, freezing meat, etc. Botswana and Namibia have a similar approach. South Africa's FMD infected zone was historically only the Kruger National Park ([Figure 7.1](#)).

Figure 7.1 Reported outbreaks of foot-and-mouth disease as published by the Agriculture, Land reform, and Rural Development Department in 2024.

Other countries do not have the same restrictions or approaches for FMD. East African countries do not have defined disease control zones for FMD, and cattle, buffalo, and other wildlife share the same rangeland.

So-called First World countries have the right to refuse a product from a country that has inadequate surveillance and disease control measures. That animal or product has the risk associated with it that it can thus introduce that disease into their own country.

A similar situation exists for African swine fever, Anthrax, TB, or any other highly infectious disease. The zones and restrictions that a country may impose on itself are not necessarily the same as for TB. Note that for many of these diseases, there are no specific disease control zones – for example, anthrax (see the map below, [Figure 7.2.](#)).

Figure 7.2 A maps representing the outbreak of Anthrax for the period 1933 to 1997.

8. DISEASE CAUSING ORGANISMS

8.1 Bacteria

Bacteria are small unicellular (single-celled) organisms that are found virtually everywhere in nature and are mostly harmless. They are large enough to be seen under an ordinary light microscope. They are typically a few micrometers long and have many shapes, including spheres, rods, and spirals. There are many thousands of bacteria known, and only a small fraction causes disease. Their classification is complex, based primarily on their staining properties using a Gram's stain (either Gram +ve or Gram -ve) and their shape.

Figure 8.1.1. Drawing of a typical light microscope. (https://lightgroup123.blogspot.com/p/blog-page_10.html)

Figure 8.1.2. Photomicrograph of bacteria ([Rocky Mountain Laboratories, NIAID, NIH](#))

Bacteria are usually carried around in the blood stream of the body and damage the cell walls of the cells that they are close to. They very seldom penetrate into a body cell. The host defense system that is the primary source of defense against bacterial infections are the white blood cells, specifically the neutrophils that attack and destroy bacteria.

They are susceptible to various antibiotics, such as penicillin and tetracyclines, which kill the bacteria. They, however, induce all kinds of toxic processes in the body, which the body has to cope with.

Diseases that are caused by bacteria are anthrax, tuberculosis, and brucellosis.

8.2 Viruses

Viruses are between 20 and 100 times smaller than bacteria and thus too small to be seen under a light microscope. They are generally only seen under sophisticated equipment. Their size varies from 0,00035 mm (poxviruses) to 0,000025 mm (polioviruses).

Most viruses are identified by special laboratory techniques that make identify antibodies to that virus (See [Figure 8.2.1](#)).

Figure 8.2.1. Electron Photomicrograph of a virus. (<https://www.abros.es/elblogdeabritos/las-enfermedades-que-afectan-a-nuestras-mascotas/rabia/>)

Figure 8.2.2. Diagrams of viruses. (<https://medium.com/@YxH4dOyC7pZzrgR/unpacking-rumors-about-the-a-i-virus-cdc68e7dfe5c>)

A viral infection often involves 100s of thousands to millions of viral particles. These can multiply at an incredible rate in the body if the conditions in the body are correct for this. Viruses can be free-floating in the blood stream or even in the GIT, but are often attach themselves to the cells of the body, and are thus unaffected by antibiotics. They come in various shapes and sizes (See **Figure 8.2.2**). The target cells can rupture and die, and if there are enough viral particles, they can cause significant damage and death.

Some viral particles stimulate cells to grow uncontrollably and produce cancers. These can be either local growths, but could also induce cancers that spread to other parts of the body.

In most instances, treatment for viral diseases do not exist. Antibiotics such as penicillin have no effect on viral infections. Some specific anti-viral drugs are available to combat HIV viruses, but are not effective against other viral infections.

Most viruses are transmitted by aerosol/water-droplet transmission, or direct contact.

Viruses induce the most significant diseases that we know – Rift Valley fever, foot-and-mouth disease, rinderpest, malignant catarrhal fever, swine fever, rabies and pox, to name but a few.

8.3 Protozoa

These are small single celled animals that are visible under a light microscope. Most live in soil or dirty water. A relatively small number occur as parasites in man and animals. They are important in ruminant and herbivore digestion.

Some are rounded or oval in shape, and may have tiny hairs on the outer edge. These tiny hairs often provide that protozoan with the ability to move (See [Figure 8.3.1](#)). Some of the protozoa have long tail-like appendages that provide that protozoan with mobility (See [Figure 8.3.2](#)).

Figure 8.3.1. Photo of a round protozoa.

Figure 8.3.2. Human African trypanosomiasis (*Trypanosoma brucei*).
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Trypanosoma sp. PHIL 613 lores.jpg](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Trypanosoma_sp._PHIL_613_lores.jpg)

Some of the diseases that are caused by protozoa include malaria, amoebic dysentery, East Coast fever, Corridor disease and nagana / sleeping sickness. Many of these organisms are transmitted by a vector of some sort – ticks, mosquitoes, but infection could be by ingesting contaminated water.

Some antibiotics are effective against protozoa, but some classes of drugs have specifically been developed to treat these infections, e.g. dysentery, Corridor disease.

8.4 Fungi

These are members of a diverse group of organisms that are not animals or plants, although are closer to simple plants. They obtain their food by absorbing nutrients from an external source.

They range from tiny, single-celled organisms invisible to the naked eye to some of the largest living multicellular organisms. They can form complex branched organisms that often cause skin infections, such as ringworm and others. (see [Figures 8.4.1](#) and [8.4.2](#))

Figure 8.4.1. Fungi in the blood. (Yehya, 2024) <https://health.ucdavis.edu/news/headlines/an-anti-inflammatory-curbs-fungi-spread-causing-serious-blood-infections/2024/06>.

Figure 8.4.2. *Dermatophilus* fungus under a microscope.
<https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/f/f6/Dermatophilus.jpg>

The skins of fungal infection are often complicated by bacterial infections (see **Figure 8.4.3**) and require both antibiotics and anti-fungal agents. If systemic fungal infections occur, they are extremely difficult to treat.

Figure 8.4.3. Fungal infection of the skin of wildebeest (<https://rrafrica.woah.org/app/uploads/2019/11/bengis2.pdf>)

8.5 Algae

The term "algae" covers many different organisms capable of producing oxygen through photosynthesis (the process of harvesting light energy from the sun to generate carbohydrates). These organisms are not necessarily closely related. However, certain features unite them, while distinguishing them from the other major group of photosynthetic organisms: the land plants.

Firstly, they lack true roots, stems and leaves, and a vascular system to circulate water and nutrients throughout their bodies. Secondly, many algae are unicellular (see [Figure 8.5.1](#)). They also occur in a variety of forms and sizes, from single celled organisms to seaweed size.

Figure 8.5.1. Light microscope photo of unicellular algae (Photo Credit: [Ye.Maltsev/Shutterstock.com](#) https://d2jx2rerrg6sh3.cloudfront.net/image-handler/picture/2021/10/shutterstock_1042159933.jpg)

Figure 8.5.2. Blue-green algae or cyanobacteria can produce toxin killing animals. (Photo Cred: Zachary Haslick) <https://www.morningagclips.com/harmful-algal-blooms-from-research-to-mitigation/>

Small unicellular algae inhabit freshwater bodies such as dams, and under the right conditions, multiply to massive numbers – a so-called algal bloom, caused by blue-green algae or cyanobacteria (see [Figure 8.5.2](#)). One organism, *Microcystis*, has been associated with die-offs of elephant.

9. VIRAL DISEASES

9.1 Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)

Epidemiology

Foot-and-mouth disease is caused by a virus and occurs in many cloven-hoofed animals such as domestic animals, buffalo, and some antelope species. Specific strains of the disease are found in different regions of the world.

Outbreaks often occur in cattle adjacent to the KNP, but outbreaks that have recently occurred elsewhere are the result of movement of infected cattle from outbreak areas adjacent to the KNP. Recent outbreaks have occurred in Gauteng, North West Province, Free State. Current outbreaks have been detected in the Eastern Cape in the Gqeberha and East London areas.

As a result of these outbreaks, our regional and international trading partners have imposed an import ban on South African live animals, meat and meat products. The economic losses from these bans have been substantial.

In South Africa, buffalo are the primary carriers of the disease – they themselves never show symptoms of the disease, but they can pass it on to other susceptible animals, which in South Africa is mainly cattle.

In East Africa, cattle, buffalo and other wildlife occur on the same rangeland, and the disease circulates through these populations all the time. None of these countries have a major export market in live cloven-hoofed animals or their products, so the economic impacts are not the result of international trade bans. The significance of this disease is however the massive production and subsequent economic losses that occur.

Symptoms:

As its name suggests, it causes lesions in the mouth and on the feet of affected animals, but very seldom causes mortality. The infected animals cannot chew or swallow their food easily, loose condition, and are lame. Animals lose condition and a serious production loss occurs.

The incubation period is 2 – 4 days. The virus multiplies in the blood and damages the mucous membranes of the mouth and tongue and the skin in those areas where it is thin – between hooves, coronet, udder, teats etc.

Figure 9.1.1. Lesions of FMD in the mouth of a cow.

The hooves may become loose and detached from the flesh and may even drop off (see [Figure 9.1.2](#)). Except where complications arise, the mouth and other lesions heal after a while and the animal recovers. Calves are, as a rule, more susceptible than older animals.

The virus is shed in the saliva, nasal discharge milk and urine. It is a highly infectious disease, and spreads very rapidly. It is, however, susceptible to heat and drying out – many disinfectants are effective against it.

Figure 9.1.2. Photos of impala hooves showing typical FMD lesions above the hooves. (Photo credits, Roy Bengis)

Figure 9.1.3. Photos of impala showing limb pain and loss of condition due to FMD infection. (Photo credits, Roy Bengis)

Mortalities sometimes result due to secondary infections of lesions, although most animals recover from these lesions.

Some wildlife species that show symptoms of infection are impala, kudu, nyala, and warthogs (see [Figure 9.1.3](#)). Warthogs can die from cardiac pathology.

Control

Because of its highly infectious nature, most countries that have the disease rely on either strict control zones (South Africa and the areas surrounding the KNP, for example), vaccination, or a combination of both. It is extremely expensive and difficult to run effective disease control zones. Most countries that do not have the disease normally will cull all infected animals in an outbreak situation rather than vaccinate.

Humans cannot contract the disease but may act as agents of spread of the infection.

9.2 Rift Valley Fever

Epidemiology

Rift Valley fever (RVF) was first described in the Rift Valley of Kenya and is a viral disease of sheep, cattle, other animals, and man and is transmitted by mosquitoes. It is a zoonosis – human beings contract the disease by being bitten by an infected mosquito but can also become infected through the handling of an infected carcass or meat or by the consumption of infected meat or milk. Sheep are the most susceptible of all the domestic animals, especially pregnant ewes and young lambs.

RVF is sporadic and appears after periods of good rain, and occurs in southern Africa about every 10 years.

Figure 9.2.1. Methods of transmission and species infected with RVF. (Diagram credit: Warimwe & Knight, 2024. Rift Valley fever. The Jenner Institute, Nuffield Dept of Medicine, Oxford).

Symptoms

Young lambs may die within a day without showing any characteristic symptoms. Some adults develop a fever, vomit and show a slimy nasal discharge. They show leg weakness and may abort. They live from 2 – 5 days and 20-30% usually die. Cases surviving for longer than 3-4 days occur amongst adult sheep and cattle. They are feverish, may abort and often show bloody diarrhea.

Figure 9.2.2. Ewe aborting as a result of RVF infection (Prof J Coetzer, University of Pretoria).
<https://www.jenner.ac.uk/research/emerging-pathogens/rift-valley-fever-rvf>

In many animals, abortion is the only symptom – in both cattle and buffalo. In cattle, bloody diarrhea is also seen.

In man, RVF induces “flu” - like symptoms with aching joints, headache and fever. It is seldom fatal but may cause serious chronic eye lesions which may lead to permanent blindness.

The most important lesions are seen in the liver, where numerous small white specks the size of a pin head are seen which is dead liver tissue. The lesions are particularly clear in young animals. There may be inflammation of the small intestine.

Economic implications

Can cause serious economic losses to domestic animals like sheep and cattle.

Treatment and prevention

There is no effective remedy but there is a good vaccine available.

Mosquito control can help to prevent the disease from spreading.

9.3. Malignant Catarrhal Fever

(Also known as Bovine malignant catarrhal fever)

Epidemiology

This disease, also known as “Snotsiekte”, is an acute and deadly viral disease affecting cattle and some other ruminants. The African form of the disease in cattle is associated with contact between cattle and blue or black wildebeest. Wildebeest does not show any symptoms. The disease has also been identified in buffalo and other antelope. The spread and epidemiology of the transmission between wildebeest and cattle is poorly understood, but is associated with stress periods in wildebeest calves, possibly around calving (see **Figure 9.3.1**). There is also a form of Snotsiekte that is sheep-associated – the clinical symptoms are identical. Biting insects may also play a role in transmission of the disease.

Figure 9.3.1. Diagram of transmission between adult and juvenile wildebeest and domestic or other animals. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368520385/figure/fig1/AS:11431281212318267@1702583750819/Epidemiological-relationships-of-AIHV-1-transmission-between-wildebeests-and-species.tif>

Clinical symptoms

The number of animals that are affected is relatively small, but nearly all the animals that are affected will die. They develop high fever, severe nasal and eye discharge that can be fluid or pus-like, corneal opacity, (Figure 9.3.2) bloody diarrhea (Figure 9.3.3) and die within 1-2 days of developing symptoms. Those that survive the first stage of infection can develop crusts around the eyes and nose, loss of condition, and death within 1-2 weeks.

Figure 9.3.2. Cow showing nasal discharge and infected eyes. (Photo credit: The Farmers Weekly, 30 April 2021: Snotsiekte vaccine in the making).

Figure 9.3.3. Photo of intestine showing bloody diarrhea. (Bristol Biomedical Image Archive, 1999, University of Bristol).

Treatment and control

There is no treatment for the disease.

Control of the disease is dependent on separation of cattle from wildebeest for at least 100-500m.

A vaccine is under development for cattle.

9.4 African Swine fever (ASF)

Epidemiology

A highly infectious viral disease of domestic pigs that causes fever, listlessness and hemorrhages (bleeding) in multiple organs in the body. Wild pig species such as warthog and bushpig are usually the source of the disease as they can harbor the virus and act as carriers, but do not show symptoms of the disease. Domestic pigs are infected by ingesting the infected tissue of a wild pig or following the bite of an infected warthog tsetse fly *Ornithodoros moubata* (**Figure 9.4.1**). These tsetse flies live in the burrows of warthogs and play an important role in the epidemiology of the disease (**Figure 9.4.2**). When the disease first breaks out amongst domestic pigs, it spreads rapidly because of the virus in the excretions and tissues of contaminated animals (blood, urine, saliva, dung, nasal discharge).

Figure 9.4.1. Diagram showing ways of transmission of African swine fever to pigs. (Anholdt et al. 2023.) *Wildl Dis* (2023) 59 (3): 465–471. <https://doi.org/10.7589/JWD-D-22-00090>

Note: Sylvatic cycle means the cycle of the organism in wild animals or the environment.

Figure 9.4.2. Warthog burrow. (Photo credit, Roy Bengis)

Figure 9.4.3. Abdominal cavity of a pig showing internal hemorrhages.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:African_swine_fever_necropsy.jpg?uselang=en#Licensing

Symptoms

In most cases, the pigs die very quickly. Bloody diarrhea, secretions from the nose and vomiting are often seen. The animals can vomit and show discolored ears feet and tail.

Abortions can be seen in animals that live long enough, and pneumonia, lack of appetite and joint inflammation can be seen. Hemorrhages are seen in the liver, heart and spleen, and the body cavities can be filled with bloody fluid (see **Figure 9.4.3**).

Control

ASF is the reason why most commercial piggeries are fenced in and the animals kept in artificial housing.

There is no treatment for this disease.

The only way to control an outbreak of this disease is to kill all sick and in-contact pigs, to destroy all the carcasses and to thoroughly disinfect cages, transport vehicles, slaughter facilities etc.

Domestic and wild pigs should not be allowed to come into contact with each other.

Classical swine fever is a similar disease, and has been introduced to parts of the Eastern Cape, where both bushpigs and warthogs act as carriers. Similarly, ASF has been introduced into parts of Eastern Europe.

9.5 Rabies

Rabies is an acute viral disease of man and all mammals and attacks the nervous system.

Epidemiology

In southern Africa, with the exception of kudu rabies in Namibia, it is transmitted by the bite of an infected animal **and is almost 100% fatal**. The most commonly infected animals are black-backed jackal, domestic dogs, yellow mongoose and bat-eared fox. Their distribution is shown in the map below, and summarized here:

- Black-backed jackal – Limpopo
- Domestic dogs – KZN and parts of the Eastern Cape
- Yellow mongoose – Free State, parts of Northern Cape, Eastern Cape, Western Cape, North West, Mpumalanga and Gauteng
- Bat-eared fox – parts of Northern Cape and Western Cape

Figure 9.5.1. Distribution of rabies vectors in South Africa.

Symptoms:

After biting, the virus travels up the nervous system to the brain, where a variety of symptoms are caused. The closer to the brain, the quicker the onset of symptoms. This can vary from 6 months to a few weeks. It also localizes in the salivary glands, which are then the organ or method of transmission. Virus in the saliva is quickly killed by drying out or heating.

In general, the most significant feature that is seen is a change in behavior. Animals that are normally tame become aggressive and bite, e.g. domestic dogs (Figure 9.5.2); aggressive wild animals can become docile without biting, have uncoordinated gait, and some bovines below continuously. Wild kudu in Namibia lose their fear of people and wander into people’s homes (Figure 9.5.3). A variety of nervous symptoms may be seen.

Figure 9.5.2. A domestic dog showing severe aggression and salivation. [Smith Collection/Gado/Getty Images 1980.](https://post.medicalnewstoday.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2021/11/rabid-dog-rabies-header-1024x575.jpg)
<https://post.medicalnewstoday.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2021/11/rabid-dog-rabies-header-1024x575.jpg>

Figure 9.5.3. A wild kudu that is affected with rabies, showing a loss a fear of people. (Credit, Prof Bob Swanepoel.)
<https://encrypted-tbn0.gstatic.com/images?q=tbn:ANd9GcShl7ej-kQKt6WQaWGKCdhqt42aVqXjkz9pmw&s>

Diagnosis of the disease is based on clinical symptoms of the species affected. Confirmation of the diagnosis is based on microscopic evaluation of the cerebellum of the brain, where characteristic Negri bodies (**Figure 9.5.4**) are seen using special stains.

Figure 9.5.4. A microscopic section of brain tissue showing characteristic black-staining Negri bodies. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Rabies_negri_bodies_brain.jpg

Treatment and control

There is no treatment other than for people, where a series of injections must be given. All infected animals that are showing symptoms must be culled to prevent the spread of the disease.

Vaccination with a killed rabies vaccine is the most efficient way of controlling this disease at a population level, and is the route of control in domestic dogs. In South Africa, vaccination of all small domestic pets is a legal requirement.

9.6 Rabbit Hemorrhagic Disease (RHD)

Epidemiology:

RHD is a disease caused by a virus and is a recent detection in South Africa. Die-offs of wild rabbits and hares from the Karoo areas in the Western and Northern Cape Provinces, but mortalities have been seen recently in Mpumalanga and Gauteng.

Carcasses of RHD-infected rabbits may be a major source for viral spreading, since the virus seems to be highly resistant and stable, even when exposed to harsh environmental conditions. At this stage it is still unclear how the disease could have entered the country, since the importation of rabbits and hares is not allowed. Investigations are underway to determine whether illegal importation could be the source.

Symptoms:

The disease results in a high number of deaths in rabbits and hares and animals die suddenly with bleeding in the organs such as the liver, kidney and spleen.

Treatment and control

Control of RHD in rabbitries relies mainly on vaccination, but the vaccine is not available in South Africa. This increases the importance of biosecurity measures in rabbitries and anywhere where rabbits or hares are kept. Rabbit owners are advised to ensure that their rabbits are secured and

must prevent any contact with other rabbits or hares, either directly or indirectly through people or equipment.

Biosecurity measures are difficult to implement in wild populations. The occurrence of RHD in the Karoo is therefore of great concern, as our indigenous Red Rock rabbit, endangered Riverine rabbit and hare species are highly susceptible to this disease

See the [Figure 9.6.1](#) provided by the Mpumalanga Veterinary Services below for a summary of the disease in rabbits

Rabbit Haemorrhagic Disease

What is
rabbit haemorrhagic
disease
?

Infection caused
by a calicivirus,

of rabbits and hares,

leading to severe liver infection and
death.

How is
rabbit haemorrhagic
disease
transmitted?

Infected
rabbits/hare
excrete the virus
and the virus is
ingested by a
healthy rabbit/hare.
Transmission
occur with direct
contact between
rabbits/hares,
or contact with contaminated
environment
or objects.

How is
rabbit haemorrhagic
disease
spread?

Movement of
people
& other
animals
Infected rabbits/hares
(live, dead, meat,
urine, droppings)
vehicles &
objects
flies & rodents
Protect your rabbit
against
rabbit haemorrhagic disease.

For more information or to report rabbit haemorrhagic disease
contact the local state veterinarian, private veterinarian, or animal health technician.

Figure 9.6.1. Rabbit hemorrhagic disease.

9.7 Avian influenza

Epidemiology

Avian influenza is a highly infectious viral disease (see [Figure 9.7.1](#)) that affects both domestic and wild birds. Avian influenza viruses have also been isolated, although less frequently, from mammalian species, including humans. This complex disease is caused by viruses divided into multiple subtypes (i.e. H5N1, H5N3, H5N8 etc.) whose genetic characteristics rapidly evolve. The disease occurs worldwide but different subtypes are more prevalent in certain regions than others.

Figure 9.7.1. H5N1 avian flu viruses (seen in gold) grow inside canine kidney cells (seen in green). (Cynthia Goldsmith/Africa CDC <https://africacdc.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/Avian-Influenza.jpg>)

The any strains of avian influenza viruses can generally be classified into two categories according to the severity of the disease in poultry:

- low severity (LPAI) that typically causes little or no clinical signs;
- high severity (HPAI) that can cause severe clinical signs and possible high mortality rates.

In birds, avian influenza viruses are shed in the feces and respiratory secretions. They can all be spread through direct contact with secretions from infected birds, especially through feces or through contaminated feed and water. Because of the resistant nature of avian influenza viruses, including their ability to survive for long periods when temperatures are low, they can also be carried on farm equipment and spread easily from farm to farm.

Where outbreaks occur in domestic birds, it is often the policy to cull all poultry, whether infected or healthy, to contain the spread of avian influenza. This represents heavy economic losses for farmers and a long-lasting impact on their livelihoods.

Migratory wild birds especially waterfowl, are natural reservoir of avian influenza viruses and they play a role in the spread the viruses across large geographical areas and also becomes victims of the disease (See [Figure 9.7.2](#)).

Figure 9.7.2. Diagram of the species that can be infected by avian influenza. (<https://rr-middleeast.woah.org/en/our-mission/one-health/highly-pathogenic-avian-influenza/>)

Symptoms

In poultry, the following can be seen:

The birds appear tired and refuse to eat. There is often a discharge from the nose, eyes and mouth. There is swelling of head, eyes, legs, combs and wattles. Coughing, sneezing and diarrhea may be present, followed by sudden death.

In humans, the following can be seen:

Abdominal pain, bleeding from the nose or gums, diarrhea, vomiting, encephalitis, and chest pain.

Although of major concern in poultry establishments in South Africa, avian influenza outbreaks have led to catastrophic mortalities in African penguin populations in the W Cape. It has also caused outbreaks in dairy cattle in North America.

Control

Where outbreaks occur in domestic birds, it is often the policy to cull all poultry, whether infected or healthy, to contain the spread of avian influenza. This represents heavy economic losses for farmers and a long-lasting impact on their livelihoods.

No vaccination is possible or effective, but vaccines are in the process of being developed for African penguins.

Avian influenza is also a major concern for public health. Whenever avian influenza viruses circulate in poultry, sporadic cases of avian influenza in humans are sometimes identified.

9.8 Mpox Disease

Mpox is a viral disease that is spreading rapidly throughout the world, and cases have been described in South Africa. It is caused by the monkeypox virus, so it is a zoonosis. This virus has been traced back to the Congo Basin and West Africa.

Symptoms

Small numbers of cases have been reported, and is transmitted by close contact with body fluids of humans, or eating contaminated bushmeat. Fever, muscle aches and sore throat appear first, followed by skin and mucosal rash. Swollen lymph nodes is also a typical feature of mpox, which is present in most cases. The focal pox virus lesions are clear, and are similar to those found in chicken pox and smallpox (which has been eradicated worldwide) (See [Figure 9.8.1](#))

Figure 9.8.1. Typical pox lesions on the back of a young boy, Course, Reuters.
<https://c.files.bbci.co.uk/fab0/live/7c7f0060-596d-11ef-aebc-6de4d31bf5cd.jpg>.

Although the current incidence in South Africa seems to be mainly in men, and particularly those living with HIV infection, children, pregnant women, and people with weak immune systems are at risk of developing complications and death from mpox.

Treatment

Treatment using specific anti-viral preparations are possible, and a vaccine is available and is being distributed world-wide.

10. BACTERIAL DISEASES

10.1 Anthrax

A bacterial disease caused by *Bacillus anthracis* that affects all mammals including man. Domestic animals are very susceptible causing heavy losses, as are wild animals. Most of the susceptible species are ungulates, but carnivores and people can also be infected (See [Figure 10.1.1.](#) and [10.1.2.](#))

Figure 10.1.1. Stained microscopic slides of anthrax bacteria ([Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine 1\(6\):496-501 DOI:10.1016/S2221-1691\(11\)60109-3](#))

Figure 10.1.2. Anthrax bacteria in the cerebrospinal fluid of the brain. (<https://www.google.com/imgres?q=bacteria%20bacillus%20cell%20anthrax%20disease>)

Epidemiology

This bacterium is a common soil organism that is ingested with food or inhaled by animals. If the organism does not come into contact with air, as in unopened carcasses, they do not produce

spores but degenerate and die after a few days in the unopened carcass. However, in the presence of air, this organism forms a resistant spore which may survive for many years in the soil and in bones.

Anthrax outbreaks are usually associated with periods of drought. This is because concentrations of spores increase in waterholes and natural pans as the volume of water decrease. The outbreaks of the disease are thus usually sporadic in South Africa.

On ingestion, the organism releases a toxin which rapidly damages the internal organs.

A number of cycles have been suggested that perpetuate the disease (see **Figure 10.1.3**):

- The direct carcass / contamination cycle
- The kudu / blowfly cycle
- The vulture / water cycle.

Figure 10.1.3. Methods of Anthrax transmission. Huang et al. 2022. “Environmental Drivers of Biseasonal Anthrax Outbreak Dynamics in Two Multihost Savanna Systems.” *Ecological Monographs* 92(4): e1526. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecm.1526>

In the wild, dead animal carcasses are opened up by predators and vultures and this can cause the disease to spread rapidly, particularly if blowflies are present. Contamination of the grazing or water is likely, and run-off water may play a role.

Figure 10.1.4. Carcass of a buffalo showing bleeding from the mouth. (Photo Roy Bengis)

Vultures especially are instrumental in spreading anthrax, although they themselves are not affected. After eating an infected carcass, they will fly to the nearest waterhole to drink. There they will defaecate and their feces have a high concentration of spores which further increases contamination in and around waterholes.

Figure 10.1.5. Vultures feeding at a carcass.

https://nationalzoo.si.edu/sites/default/files/styles/wide/public/conservation/ghp_vulture_001.jpg?itok=gGspAkrb

Figure 10.1.5. Blowflies sitting on the leaves and branches of trees (left) around an anthrax carcass and contaminating browse (right). From: Bengis & Freaun, 2014. Revue scientifique et technique. OIE

Kudu then come and eat the leaves, and then ingest some of the blowfly droppings, which may contain the anthrax organism, and then get infected that way.

Figure 10.1.6. Kudu eating leaves off trees which may be anthrax contaminated.
<https://pixabay.com/photos/kudu-buck-kruger-reserve-2060383/>

Symptoms

Several forms of the disease can be found.

The per-acute or acute form (i.e. the course of the disease is very rapid) results in death of the animal within hours of contracting the disease, mostly showing few symptoms prior to death - swelling on the body, especially on the neck and chest may be seen.

Chronic or more delayed onset of symptoms are often found alive before dying show a high fever, shivering, trembling and sometimes diarrhea. There are often signs of struggling where the carcass is found and profuse dark, tarry blood can be found oozing from all body openings – nose, mouth, anus. Anthrax carcasses decompose rapidly because the blood does not clot properly. The carcasses typically are found with a head or neck reflected backwards (**Figure 10.1.7**).

Figure 10.1.7. Carcass of a giraffe that had died of anthrax showing typically turned back neck and head. (Photo: Roy Bengis)

Figure 10.1.8. Carcass of a kudu that died of anthrax showing a tarry bloody discharge from the anus, and signs of paddling of limbs on the ground. (Source, P.T. Nel, SAWC)

Herbivores typically show tarry bloody discharges from nose and anus (see [Figure 10.1.3](#) and [Figure 10.1.8](#)).

Carnivores often show a swollen face ([Figure 10.1.9](#)).

Figure 10.1.9. Lions that had died from anthrax often show a swollen face. (Photos: Roy Bengis)

There is also a form of the disease which occurs on the skin, particularly in humans, and is often referred to as wool sorters disease from the time when people were infected by domestic sheep wool. Fatalities can occur.

Diagnosis:

Usually bleeding from the anus or nostrils.

NEVER CUT open a carcass that is showing these symptoms. This will allow the organism to form a spore stage which is the infective stage. Resulting in spread of the disease.

Only a small incision should be made (the ear is a good place) to collect a drop of blood for a blood smear (See **Figure 10.1.10**).

The bacilli can be seen as rod-shaped organisms in a blood smear and have a particular red brick coloration.

Figure 10.1.10. Diagram of the process of making a blood smear. (Source P.T. Nel, SAWC)

Treatment and control of the disease:

The treatment of valuable individual animals and humans at risk with penicillin is effective.

There is a very effective vaccine – animals can be vaccinated with drop-out darts from a helicopter, but it is impractical to vaccinate large populations or areas of animals.

Carcasses should by law be burnt or buried, but this is impractical, especially where the disease is endemic.

Many conservation agencies in other countries leave the carcasses where they are until the disease has burnt itself out.

10.2 Tuberculosis

Epidemiology

Various forms of tuberculosis are found – bovine TB (*Mycobacterium bovis*), human TB (*M. tuberculosis*) avian TB (*M. avium*) and others. *Mycobacterium bovis* is the most important bacteria affecting wild herbivores.

Bovine tuberculosis (BTB) was first detected in Kruger National Park (KNP) in a single African buffalo in 1990, mostly likely from contact with an infected cow. It has since spread into most other species, and has spread up into GonaReZhou National Park in Zimbabwe.

Clinical symptoms

The bacterium enters the body usually via the respiratory or oral route, and various forms of TB can be found. Respiratory or lung TB is the most common, but organ TB is seen as well, where the liver, spleen, intestines and other organs are affected.

The most significant symptom that is seen is weight loss (see [Figure 10.2.1](#)), but clinical signs include coughing, enlarged lymph nodes, (see [Figure 10.2.2](#)) and coarse coat in chronic cases. Wild animals show few clinical signs, but when they do the disease is usually in an advanced stage.

Figure 10.2.1. A lion showing severe weight loss as a result of tuberculosis infection. (Photo: Roy Bengis)

Figure 10.2.2. Kudu showing enlarges lymph nodes below the jaw, with ulceration. (Photo: Roy Bengis)

Figure 10.2.3. Lesions of bovine TB in the lungs of buffalo can be either small nodules (L top) or large abscess-like lesions (R top) and below. (Photos: Roy Bengis, KNP)

Typically, it forms focal nodules or various sizes, which may be encapsulated or hardened, or it may be large diffuse lesions in the lungs (see **Figure 10.2.3**). These are then coughed up, and

other in contact animals may pick up the infection. Signs of infection can also be seen on the membranes lining the lung cavity or abdominal cavity (see [Figure 10.2.4](#)).

Figure 10.2.4. TB lesions on the mesenteries of the abdominal cavity. (Photo: Roy Bengis)

Other excretory products such as urine, feces and milk also carry the bacteria and can contaminate the food and water of wild animals. Predators and scavengers can contract the disease by eating the meat of infected animals – lions have been particularly affected, but scavengers such as hyena have not.

Diagnosis

In domestic animals, buffalo and lions, diagnosis is by performing an intra-dermal skin test, but in most wild animals, diagnosis is based on a post-mortem examination and microscopic examination (see [Figure 10.2.5](#)).

Figure 10.2.5. TB testing in buffalo – collection of blood samples and reading of a skin test. (Photos : Roy Bengis, KNP)

Treatment and prevention:

It has serious ecological implications and scientists do not, at present, know how to contain the spread of the disease. What makes this disease so serious is the fast rate of spread and the fact that many species can be affected.

- Limit the movement or relocation of susceptible animals – especially buffalo and kudu – from areas where TB occurs.
- Where wildlife and domestic cattle are kept on the same property, cattle should be tested annually.
- Wild animals which appear emaciated (thin) and have a rough coat should be shot and an autopsy performed by a state vet.
- The treatment of wild animals is not practical and is not recommended. Treatment of infected humans consists of daily treatment, and these are not effective in most wild animals.
- There is, at present, no effective TB vaccine for wild animals. Research into this is however ongoing. A good vaccine exists for humans which is given soon after birth.

10.3 Brucellosis (Contagious abortion)

Epidemiology

This bacterial disease causes severe abortions, particularly in buffalo and cattle. The causative organism is *Brucella abortus*.

The disease has been found in hippo, zebra, impala, eland and waterbuck (see [Figure 10.3.1](#)).

In sable, *Brucella melitensis* causes bursitis (swollen joints).

Brucellosis in wildlife

Figure 10.3.1. Diagram of wildlife species affected by *Brucella abortus*. (©Prof H van Heerden, Faculty of Veterinary Science, University of Pretoria)

Symptoms

Severe abortion and retained placenta can be seen in female animals (see [Figure 10.3.2 a and b](#)), but orchitis (testicular infection) can be seen in bulls. Bursitis (joint infection) (see [Figure 10.3.3](#)) can also be seen in cattle and buffalo.

Although both bulls and cows can be affected, the cow is the major source of infection – either by aborted fetuses and fetal membranes or uterine discharge. Milk or colostrum can also be infected, and the cow can pass this onto the calf. Semen can be contaminated with the organism, which can be transmitted at mating.

The levels of abortion can be significant in buffalo, and it is easily transmitted to cattle by aerosol or droplet infection, or transmitted by flies.

Figure 10.3.2a. Aborted buffalo fetus. (Credit Roy Bengis, Skukuza, KNP)

Figure 10.3.2b. Retained placenta in cattle. (Photos: Courtesy of Dr Blasco; <https://repository.up.ac.za/handle/2263/3271>).

Figure 10.3.3. Hygroma/bursitis in a buffalo leg (Photo credit: Roy Bengis, KNP).

In humans, typical symptoms of infection include severe night sweating, sore throat, joint and muscle pain, headache, and weakness. Sometimes the infection is never lost, and recurrences occur for many years after treatment.

Treatment and control

It is a disease of significance with regard to movement of buffalo outside of the FMD free zone of South Africa, as animals must be tested negative before movement. The occurrence of the disease in a closed herd can be erratic, as the disease can skip up to 2 generations before cases are seen again, or before animals test positive again. This makes control and testing for negative animals very difficult.

There is a cattle vaccine (Strain 19 vaccine and RB 51), but it has not been validated in buffalo or wildlife.

It is a zoonosis, and people can become infected by coming into contact with fetal fluids and membranes, and eating contaminated fetal remains. Always practice care such as washing of hands or wear gloves.

11. PROTOZOAL DISEASE

11.1 Trypanosomiasis /Trypanosomosis

Epidemiology

This is caused by a variety of *Trypanosoma* species (see [Figure 11.1.1](#)). In humans, this is known as sleeping sickness, and in animals as nagana. This protozoan parasitic disease of vertebrate animals affects cattle, water buffalo, sheep, goats, horses, pigs, dogs and other species. It is seen in a blood smear as a free-floating elongated organism, typically with a wavy outline and a long whip-like tail

It is transmitted by tsetse flies of the genus *Glossina*, and occurs from the southern edge of the Sahara desert to Zimbabwe, Angola and Mozambique.

It is estimated to be about 3 million cattle annually losses directly attributed to trypanosomosis from reduced meat and milk production, and the cost of treatment and vector control run into the millions of US dollars.

Figure 11.1.1. A blood smear showing *Trypanosoma* organisms. Source: Centre for Disease Control 2006

Figure 11.1.2. A tsetse fly. (<https://www.kznhealth.gov.za/enviro/vector/tsetsefly.htm>)

Most trypanosomes develop for one to a few weeks in tsetse flies which act as biological vectors. The parasites are transmitted to the host animal in saliva when a fly bites the host. Trypanosomes can also be spread by other means such as surgical instruments and mechanical vectors such as biting flies including horse flies.

Symptoms

The incubation period for nagana is four days to approximately eight weeks. Although acute cases may be seen, trypanosomosis is often a chronic disease in susceptible animals. Trypanosomes infect the blood of the host causing fever, weakness, lethargy and anemia, which lead to weight loss and a reduction in fertility and milk production.

Control

Nagana can be controlled by reducing tsetse fly populations with traps and insecticides. Animals can be given anti-parasitic drugs prophylactically in areas with a high population of trypanosome-infected tsetse flies.

Infected animals can be treated with drugs, but drug resistance has been observed. The selection of trypanosome tolerant breeds of cattle can lessen the impact of infection.

No vaccine is available to prevent trypanosomiasis.

11.2 Corridor Disease and East Coast Fever

Corridor disease (CD) in southern Africa is caused by a protozoal organism called *Theileria parva* (see **Figure 11.2.1**) and is closely related to East Coast fever in East Africa which is caused by the same organism. It is named after the strip between the Hluhluwe and Mfolozi game reserves in KwaZulu Natal (KZN) where the disease was first described.

In Southern Africa this disease is associated with buffalo, where the buffalo are permanent carriers of the disease if they are infected. This means they never show any symptoms but they can transmit this to other susceptible animals, in this case domestic cattle. The buffalo do not die, but the cattle do die after infection within the first 10-20 days with 100 % mortality of the infected animals.

This disease is transmitted by the brown ear tick, (see [Figure 11.2.2](#)). The tick feeds on infected buffalo, drop to the ground and then attach and feed on cattle if on the same pasture.

Figure 11.2.1. Corridor disease organism in red blood cells – see arrow. (Source: Financial Times. https://encrypted-tbn0.gstatic.com/images?q=tbn:ANd9GcQe0KyCgoMM6B1cA3Aa1e2-j1deC_nDeVMzDA&s)

Figure 11.2.2. The brown ear tick, transmitter of Corridor disease. (Source: Science Direct.) <https://encrypted-tbn0.gstatic.com/images?q=tbn:ANd9GcSE1ADClfZ0onoe0OKKOkvxfTj87h6Af1ZzA&s>)

Infected ticks can survive for up to 18 months under laboratory conditions, so removal of all buffalo on infected farms and quarantine for this disease is 2 years in South Africa.

There are areas of South Africa that are designated Corridor infected areas, such as areas around the Kruger National Park and parts of the eastern KZN, but are subject to strict movement control. (see [Figure 11.2.3](#))

Figure 11.2.3. Distribution of the brown ear tick species. (Prof Maxime Madder, Prof Ivan Horak, Dr Hein Stoltz) https://www.afrivip.org/sites/default/files/07_identification_vetimportance.pdf

Distribution of the tick

The brown ear tick is distributed from the Eastern Cape all the way into Kenya and the DRC. It is not found in the drier parts of Africa. The relevance of this disease is related to buffalo the buffalo industry in South Africa - all buffalo that are caught and sold within the FMD free zone have to be tested for CD with a negative result.

Symptoms

Cattle may have a fever, show swollen lymphatic glands, have running eyes and nose and walk with swaying hindquarters. Their appetite is poor and there is a rapid loss of condition. There may be diarrhea. The animal eventually becomes too weak to rise, froths from the nostrils and dies.

Diagnosis of the disease is done on post mortem examination, with multiple focal small white sports seen on many internal organs such as the liver, kidney and spleen.

12. NEW DISEASES

12.1 Peste des petits ruminants (PPR)

This highly infectious viral disease affects small stock and antelope, such as ibex and gazelles (see [Figure 12.1.1](#)). Although cattle and pigs can be infected, they do not develop any clinical signs, and is the small stock equivalent of rinderpest.

Figure 12.1.1. The epidemiological cycle of PPR. (Adapted from Charbonnier and Laveissiere, 2015)

Figure 12.1.2. Global distribution of PPR at different time periods. (Adapted from Yongxi Dou et al., 2020)

Distribution

The disease is widespread in many parts of the world including most of Africa, the Middle East, the Indian sub-continent (Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, etc.) and China (See **Figure 12.1.1**). It is not in South Africa yet, but should be viewed with concern given the massive increase in distribution of the disease in the last number of years

Symptoms include fever, eye and nasal discharges, sores in the mouth, diarrhea, listlessness, cough and pneumonia, abortion and death with fatality rates of up to 90 %

There is a very effective vaccine available where the disease currently occurs.

Other organisms or conditions that can produce disease

There are a variety of internal parasites, external parasites (ectoparasites), nutritional factors poisonings that can induce disease. Some are easy to identify and quantify, others not.

13. EXTERNAL PARASITES

Within this group are ticks, mosquitoes, lice, flies and their larvae and mites. Some of these ectoparasites are also of significance as vectors of disease. Some are purely blood suckers, and can induce significant anemia and dehydration, others actually secrete a toxin that can have painful local effects, or even paralysis of the host.

13.1 Ticks

Ticks are of the same family as scorpions and crabs, and have 8 legs as adults. Two major kinds of ticks are found – hard ticks and soft ticks. Both of them can cause severe effects as blood suckers, but can transmit disease. They are extremely adaptable, and are extremely effective at colonizing new habitats if transported to new areas, particularly if the habitats are suitable for their propagation.

Even a single tick can cause significant problems in wildlife. They can transmit diseases (e.g. corridor disease and heartwater), cause severe ulceration with secondary infections and can cause animals to become anemic, lose condition and become more susceptible to diseases.

Most wild animal species have ticks. Ticks are protected by a hard shield.

As a general rule, blue wildebeest and smaller game species are host to immature ticks whilst larger species such as buffalo, giraffe, eland and kudu are host to both mature and immature tick parasites. Tick loads increase during certain months of the year. Ticks species have a preference for attaching themselves to certain parts of an animal's body – for example the areas of the body where the skin is thinner (see [Figure 13.1.3](#)).

Blue wildebeest are unusual large mammals in that they have very few adult ticks.

All ticks have a life cycle, during which they grow from the egg stage, through larval and nymph stages until they are adult ticks. They have strong biting mouth parts, and have different number of legs at stages of their life cycle. The larvae have 6 legs, and the nymphae and adults have 8 legs. At each of these stages beyond the egg, they need to feed on a blood meal to mature their bodies so they can undergo a metamorphosis to the next stage of their life cycle (see [Figure 13.1.1](#)). Some of these stages are minute – so called 'pepper ticks', but as adults, the females can be engorged with blood which they need for maturation of their eggs before they are laid. Some of these ticks need 2 to 3 hosts to complete their life cycle.

Ticks are incredibly responsive to carbon dioxide, and will identify the presence of a host by the excessive amount of CO₂ that animals produce. Many ticks will actually seek out the source of this and attach to them.

Figure 13.1.1. Diagram of life cycle of ticks.
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Life_cycle_of_ticks_family_ixodidae.PNG

Figure 13.1.2. Showing the hard ticks of the group Ixodidae. (Photo Credit: California Department of Public Health).

Hard ticks occupy many different habitats in southern Africa, from arid, semi-arid bushveld areas to forest. These are the most significant group of ticks from a disease transmission point of view. The lengths of a complete life cycle is about 2 years, during which the female can lay up to 15,000 eggs.

Treating of wildlife for ticks in open ecosystems is not practical and a debatable procedure. They are part of the ecosystem, and most wildlife species have adapted to their presence. It is really when you have open rangeland systems where cattle and wildlife mix that treating cattle for ticks may be required.

Regular dipping of cattle for ticks in the FMD control zones is largely a way of inspecting cattle for outbreaks of FMD at the dip tank.

Figure 13.1.3. Preferred attachment sites of hard ticks are in the groin or under the legs. (Photo credits, Roy Bengis)

The diseases that hard ticks transmit to domestic animals are Corridor disease, redwater, biliary in dogs and anaplasmosis in cattle. Buffalo that are not infected with Corridor disease can be infected by brown ear ticks that harbor the disease.

Soft ticks or tampans generally are not as resistant nor as widely spread as hard ticks, but are significant in farming communities (see **Figure 13.1.4**). They have an odd shaped abdomen, where the legs seem to come out from underneath the body.

Figure 13.1.4. An example of a soft tick. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ornithodoros_savignyi

One species lives in the Kalahari, is nocturnal and come out mainly at night, and can induce paralysis of sheep and lambs.

Another species inhabits the burrows of warthogs, and feed off the warthogs there. In this way, they will perpetuate the cycle of African swine fever virus that they obtain from the warthogs to babies or new individuals. This is why commercial piggeries in ASF areas are kept on concrete or solid floors.

13.2 Fleas and lice

Fleas are members of the class of insects and have 6 legs as adults. They are smaller than ticks, but are significant in terms of irritation on certain thin skin animals. They are active over the whole body of the animal, hiding between the hairs. They are more of concern in carnivores and birds, and cause little damage to thicker skinned animals such as buffalo antelope, elephant and rhino.

Like ticks, they also undergo a life cycle from eggs, larvae, nymphae and adults (see Figure 13.2.1).

Figure 13.2.1. Diagram of the life cycle of the flea. <https://puainta.com/blogs/cats/flea-in-cats-causes-symptoms-and-treatment>.

Figure 13.2.2. Photo of fleas between the hairs of a dog. https://printourpet.com/cdn/shop/articles/63b3a67f-f9c4-4de6-b800-26f5de71336e.jpeg_800x.png?v=1660072216

A massive infestation of fleas on a bird or carnivore can literally suck all the blood out of that animal. This should however be cause for consideration, in that there may be something wrong with the animal, or something that is out of balance in the ecosystem.

Lice

Lice also part of the insect group. Their life cycle also has stages that include eggs, larvae, nymphae and adults (**Figure 13.2.3**). They can be found on a number of wild animals including carnivores, antelope and warthog. The eggs are attached to body hairs and are easily visible and are often called 'nits'.

They are of less significance to animals than fleas but can be of significance in wild birds.

Figure 13.2.3. The life cycle of a sucking louse. (Image credit Madison Mayfield)

Figure 13.2.4. Comparison between fleas and lice. (Photo Credit: Ed Reschke/ Getty Images - <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/flea-vs-lice#symptoms>)

13.3 Flies

Flies are part of the insect family, and have a typical eggs, larvae, pupa and adult fly cycle

Tsetse flies

Tsetse flies are significant carriers of trypanosome parasite, and cause sleeping sickness in people and nagana in cattle.

Their bite is painful, and their distribution is limited to certain areas of southern Africa.

Figure 13.3.1. Drawing and photo of a tsetse fly. (Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia, 2024, October 11). tsetse fly. Encyclopedia Britannica. [https://www.britannica.com/animal/tsetse-fly.](https://www.britannica.com/animal/tsetse-fly))

Spraying of insecticides in certain areas has eradicated many of the species of tsetse fly that are responsible for causing sleeping sickness. The tsetse is a true parasite – it can only survive by feeding on the blood of vertebrate animals. They have a characteristic stance and a hammer or hatchet shaped cell in the wing.

Figure 13.3.2. The characteristic hatchet shaped cell in the wing of a tsetse fly. (https://live.staticflickr.com/3226/5852275477_ee0d5cea07_z.jpg)

House flies and biting flies

These are the agents that annoy us all, but they have a significant function in cleaning up residues of food and detritus.

Figure 13.3.3. Image of a house fly. <https://shop.insectscience.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/HOUSE-FLY-ILLUSTRATION.jpg>

Blow or carrion flies

Figure 13.3.4. Image of a blow fly. <https://www.shutterstock.com/image-photo/close-blow-fly-carrion-bluebottles-600nw-1950477229.jpg>

Blowflies or carrion flies are a critical part of the ecosystem – their role as consumers of carcasses and the turnover of nutrients is significant. Their ability to transmit disease is also relevant, particularly from anthrax infected carcasses, and the deposition of their contaminated saliva on leaves is then a source of anthrax to other species.

Louse flies

Figure 13.3.5. A louse that could be found crawling in bird feathers. (<https://encrypted-tbn2.gstatic.com/images?q=tbn:ANd9GcTuPirNkygfltjxGMODCkTDaWTJzVLYqW-FC129JcWfGtQFYe>)

These are not of major significance, but can be seen crawling under the feathers of birds, particularly pigeons. They are also sometimes seen crawling under the thick fur of carnivores and antelope.

13.4 Mosquitoes and midges

Mosquitoes (*Anopheles sp.*) are really important vectors or transmitters of human and avian malaria. Females and males can feed off plant sap, but the females need to have a blood meal to mature their eggs. The males are generally not biting insects. They have for centuries played in a role in limiting human encroachment into wildlife areas, but the use of modern antimalarial drugs and their habitat destruction have made their impact on human encroachment less.

Figure 13.4.1 An engorged mosquito. <https://cdn.mos.cms.futurecdn.net/vSpz6id3RqS6N2ro9GumKe.jpg>

Midges (*Culicoides sp.*) have played a major role in the spread of Rift Valley fever and diseases such as bluetongue, Wesselsbron disease.

Figure 13.4.2 An example of a midge.

<https://res.cloudinary.com/hillsboroughcounty/image/upload/v1687587401/Web/Images/Global/midge%20v%20mosquito%20copy.png>

13.5 Mites

These are tiny tick-like animals (see **Figure 13.5.1** and **Figure 13.5.3**) that live largely on the skin of a number of host species, causing mange, and in the upper passages of the lungs and air-sacs of birds where it caused significant irritation and subsequent infection.

In the skin of parasitized animals, the skin can be severely thickened, (see **Figure 13.5.2**) with areas of hair loss. This can be focal areas, but can involve the whole body. These animals are often immune compromised, and are a reflection of an imbalance in the ecosystem in some way. The condition is treatable, but the underlying causes that lead to the infestation must be sought.

Figure 13.5.1. A skin mite under a microscope. https://d2jx2rerrg6sh3.cloudfront.net/image-handler/picture/2021/4/shutterstock_1350477944-1.jpg

Figure 13.5.2. A jackal with mange. (Photo credit, Roy Bengis)

Figure 13.5.3. Bird mite infestation on human hand.

https://cdn-cegel.nitrocdn.com/jONEeEydypVHjtsqWAQoTqPUUyToBbKw/assets/images/optimized/rev-c29120c/envirosafepestcontrol.com.au/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/bird_mites_on_skin.jpg

14. INTERNAL PARASITES OR WORMS

Internal parasite infestation in wildlife is not a major concern, unless they are artificially housed and fed. In most semi-arid bushveld scenarios, unless there is major habitat and population mismanagement, animals cope with parasites well.

There are three major groups of internal parasites or worms (helminths) :

- Roundworms or nematodes (**Figure 14.1**)
- Tapeworms or cestodes (**Figure 14.2**)
- Flukes or trematodes (**Figure 14.3**)

Figure 14.1. Roundworms in the intestine of a horse.

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Slawomir-Kornas-2/publication/6395030/figure/fig1/AS:983845172170757@1611578376739/Small-intestine-of-the-foal-blocked-by-the-roundworms-Department-of-Zoology-and-Ecology_Q320.jpg

Most species of wildlife have internal parasites of one form or another. These species of roundworms are generally specific to a wildlife species, and do not readily cross from one wild animal to another.

Most helminths have an intermediate host that allows the parasite to maintain itself in this transport host.

Figure 14.2. Tapeworm in human intestine. <https://encrypted-tbn0.gstatic.com/images?q=tbn:ANd9GcTgcjNdTCWZopPehlzW1ILHsdT5Fw-gJzksqQ&s>

Figure 14.3. The head of a tapeworm. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.britannica.com%2Fscience%2Fcestodiasis&psig=AOvVaw2ss3GYKG72RRuWcbeKao7>

The exception to this is some of the kinds of tapeworms. Some tape worms have dogs or sheep as final hosts, but if humans for example come into contact with or ingest fecal material from dogs, they develop cysts in the brain and other organs. These are not easily treatable, and surgery is sometimes needed to remove these cysts.

Flukes are generally associated with water bodies, and have snails as the intermediate hosts. They are very seldom a problem, unless wildlife or people are forced to live or to be close to these infected water sources. Bilharzia is one of these.

Figure 14.3. A photo of a liver fluke. (photo AfriVIP, Prof Joop Boomke Onderstepoort).

15. FUNGAL INFECTIONS

Fungal infections in wildlife are not common. *Dermatophilus* infestation causes skin lesions in carnivores, antelope (see **Figure 15.1**) and other species, and is often complicated by hot moist or wet conditions. It is usually spread from one animal to another by direct contact, and is often related to stress, a drop in immunity or conditions of intensification.

Figure 15.1. *Dermatophilus* skin infection in blue wildebeest. (Roy Bengis, 2019) <https://rr-africa.woah.org/app/uploads/2019/11/bengis2.pdf>

Aspergillus sp fungal infections are usually seen as respiratory infections, particularly in birds, where infection of the lungs and air sacs are present.

16. NUTRITIONAL CONDITIONS

Simple nutritional conditions that involve wildlife are usually related to the condition of the habitat or ecosystem that they are in.

The major components of an animal's nutrition needs are protein and energy. Where either or both of these are lacking, then the animal's needs will not be adequately met. Carbohydrates are also important, as are a variety of minerals and micro-nutrients.

The major minerals that are required to sustain animal's growth or well-being are sodium, chloride, calcium and phosphate, which are essential to adequate bone growth. Micro-nutrient such as zinc, magnesium, manganese, and molybdenum.

Every animal has a feeding strategy and habitat to which they are best suited. Most antelope and bovids (cattle and buffalo) are largely grass eaters, but some species such as giraffe, kudu bushbuck and nyala are browsers, eating leafy material from trees. White rhino and zebra are grazers, but black rhino are browsers. Elephant consume up to 60 % grass, the rest leaves and bark. Some species are generalist, and can consume either, depending on availability, such as impala and eland.

The most significant factor that affects these nutrients in wildlife is drought. This applies equally to carnivores and herbivores, as the entire ecosystem is affected. Not only is plant material in short supply for the herbivores, but insect and small prey items are no longer in abundance. This has an effect higher up the food chain, and will affect carnivores as well.

Disturbances in habitat in a certain area, as particular grass species or food items may disappear. This can be over a short- or long-term period, with a change from bushveld to grassland, and in the case of vegetation clearing, the other way around is possible.

Most African savannah biomes are fire adapted. Fire is a significant regenerative tool as it removes moribund vegetation and allows new vegetation to form. The primary agent for inducing fires is lightning, but spontaneous combustion in a pile of detritus is also possible. The lack of fire and overgrazing has the potential to transform a landscape of an open savannah woodland into an impenetrable bush-encroached thicket. Fynbos in the Western Cape needs to burn every 8-12 years, while savannah woodland needs to burn every 4-6 years. Highveld grasslands can burn every 2-3 years. Over burning an area can also be detrimental, especially if human induced. This is a significant feature where pastoralist communities and wildlife overlap.

Where animals are kept in fenced areas or some form of intensification, the nutritional needs of each species will need to be carefully considered, monitored and adjusted if required. A lack of understanding of these needs and the balance that needs to be maintained can result in disease of some form.

17. POISONINGS

17.1 Naturally occurring poisons

Many naturally occurring and synthetic substances are used for agricultural purposes, but also for the indiscriminate poisoning of vultures (see [Figure 17.1.1](#)) and some carnivores. Much of this is for traditional or cultural purposes in rural communities.

Figure 17.1.1. Mass mortality of vulture as a result of poisoning. (Photo credit, Roy Bengis)

Arsenic is a natural component of the earth's crust and is widely distributed throughout the environment in the air, water and land. It is highly toxic. Because arsenic is tasteless, colorless, and odorless, testing is needed for detection

People are exposed to elevated levels of inorganic arsenic through drinking contaminated water, using contaminated water in food preparation and irrigation of food crops, industrial processes, eating contaminated food and smoking tobacco.

Long-term exposure to inorganic arsenic, mainly through drinking-water and food, can lead to chronic arsenic poisoning. Skin lesions and skin cancer are the most characteristic effects. Its use is supposed to be limited, but it is still available and probably the most commonly used.

Strychnine is a highly toxic colorless, bitter substance, used as a pesticide particularly for killing small vertebrates such as birds and rodents. When inhaled, swallowed, or absorbed through the eyes or mouth, causes poisoning which results in muscular convulsions and eventually death through lack of oxygen.

Lead poisoning is usually the result in individual scavengers such as vultures or ground hornbills where they consume lead shot or bullets in carcasses killed by hunters using lead-based ammunition (see [Figure 17.1.2](#)).

Figure 17.1.2. X-ray of a ground hornbill with lead pellets in the stomach (Photo credit Lucy Kemp).

Symptoms in humans may include abdominal pain, constipation, headaches, irritability, memory problems infertility. Some of the effects are permanent. In severe cases, anemia, convulsions coma and death may occur.

It is treatable.

17.2 Plant toxicity

Plant toxicity in wildlife is rare. Wild animals have an almost innate ability to detect or know when something is poisonous. The only significant toxicity that may occur is when wildlife are translocated to an area that they are unfamiliar with.

For example, gifblaar (see [Figure 17.2.1](#)) is one of the first plants to turn green in a savannah biome, and if consumed, causes sudden mortalities in cattle. It is possible that an antelope species that is unfamiliar with it may consume the leaves with subsequent mortality.

Figure 17.2.1. Gifblaar (*Dichapetalum cymosa*) in early spring. (Source Tsammalex. Prof Christo Botha, University of Pretoria http://media.eol.org/data_objects/27160777)

There are hundreds of plants toxic to cattle and sheep, but the incidence of poisoning in wildlife is largely unknown, but not likely to be common.

Figure 17.2.2. Fruit of the Green Monkey Apple tree, (*Strychnos pungens*) which is mildly toxic. (Source: Wikipedia.

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/thumb/a/a0/Strychnos_pungens%2C_vrug%2C_Little_Eden.jpg/704px-Strychnos_pungens%2C_vrug%2C_Little_Eden.jpg)

Algal blooms, caused by blue-green algae or cyanobacteria, can occur in freshwater dams or lakes, and mortalities as a result of this have been reported in elephant in the KNP and Botswana.

Figure 17.2.3. Algal blooms on the side of dams. (Source: Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency)

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

So by this stage you have a good idea of some of the diseases and risks associated with trying to find out what a single animal or group or animals has died of.

In order to finalize this process, remember that there are often people who have more information or background on this than you do.

The first people you will think of to assist you are the relevant State Veterinary Department – either the State Veterinarian directly or an Animal Health Technician appointed to that office.

A lot of the assistance that you require will need to be discussed with them beforehand, and their availability to come out to remote locations. This will require their cooperation in sending off samples in formalin, blood smears or swabs for bacterial culture. Find out where their offices are and obtain their contact details.

- Contact them
- Describe the symptoms or circumstances of the mortality
- Ask them to assist – come to examine the carcass or case

If they are unavailable, then try to do what you can, unless the state vet expressly forbids it – for example in the area surrounding an anthrax outbreak.

In all instances, you must provide as much information as you can – consult the sample submission information sheet. If you cannot provide any information, that sample will be get lost in a pile of 100s of others, and will have little to no value. A little bit of information such as species, sex, age and location and what the sample is will be invaluable.

Thanks from the Training Team!